

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

IONIC LIQUIDS IN THE PROCESS OF 1-OCTENE OLIGOMERIZATION

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Abstract

In the article, an ionic liquid catalytic system based on diethylamine hydrochloride and aluminum chloride (AlCl₃), which meets the concepts of “Green Chemistry,” is synthesized as an object of study. The process of 1-octene oligomerization was carried out in the presence of synthesized ionic liquid catalyst systems. The structure, chemical composition and physicochemical properties of fractions obtained by oligomerization were studied. As a result of experimental studies, fractions above 350⁰C were obtained and have high quality indicators.

Keywords: ionic liquid, oligomerization, 1-octene

1. Introduction

Recently, the interest of chemical researchers in ionic liquids has been growing rapidly. Thus, with their application, environmentally friendly technologies in petrochemical processes have increased significantly. As is known, the chemical and physical properties of ionic liquids depend on the structure and nature of the cations and anions included in their composition. By changing the structure of these anions and cations, they can be easily tuned. Depending on the ions present in ionic liquids, they can be neutral, basic or acidic in nature. The properties of ionic liquids of Lewis acids depend on the nature of the anion and the molar ratio of organic cation to inorganic anion. Numerous studies conducted with ionic liquids have shown that a wide range of chemical reactions can be carried out in their presence. Ionic liquids based on Lewis acids, such as AlCl₃, are considered ionic liquid catalysts. In recent years, research has been intensively developing in the field of oligomerization and polymerization of olefins with the participation of ionic liquids and the possibility of creating new effective technological schemes based on them [1-3].

Our article is devoted to the preparation of oligomeric fractions based on chloroaluminate catalytic systems. Their fractional and structural compositions, molecular weight distribution and physicochemical properties were determined. They have an oligoalkyl-naphthenic structure.

The goal of our research is to obtain oligomers with a maximum content of oil fractions and a minimum number of double bonds in the structure for use as PAO oils. In this chapter the results of researches are included on oligomerization of 1-octene with the use of chloroaluminate type ionic-liquid compositions as the catalysts.

2. Experimental part

Work on the synthesis of components and catalytic systems, as well as the method of oligomerization of 1-octene, was carried out in an inert atmosphere using feedstock and reagents purified by distillation.

The following reactants were used in the work:

Dried over calcined Al₂O₃, 1-octene was purified by distillation (boiling point 122-123⁰C) at atmospheric pressure.

AlCl₃ was stored in closed containers in an inert atmosphere.

Since dimethylamine hydrochloride is hygroscopic, it is dried under vacuum before the experiment.

Chloroaluminate ionic liquids were prepared on the basis of AlCl₃ with amino complexes in various molar ratios.

The synthesis of ionic-liquid catalytic systems, as well as the oligomerization of 1-octene, was carried out in a thermostated glass reactor in a dry nitrogen atmosphere.

For this purpose, before preparing the complex catalyst, the reactor was first thoroughly evacuated while heated in a nitrogen flow. The corresponding amino hydrochloride is then added to the reactor at room temperature.

The required amount of AlCl₃ was added to it in a nitrogen flow. The catalyst was prepared at room temperature for 2-5 minutes. The following ionic-liquid catalysts were prepared using this method:

In our studies, ionic liquids were used as acid catalysts, mainly for the oligomerization of 1-octene with an excess of AlCl₃:

In general, these transitions can be given as follows:

Apparently, by taking an excess amount of AlCl₃, it is possible to change the nature of the catalyst, which in turn affects the kinetic regularities and mechanism of oligomerization of octene-1.

The synthesized ionic liquids are yellowish viscous liquids at room temperature.

After obtaining the complex catalyst, 1-octene was added to it through a dropping funnel with constant stirring. The oligomerization process was carried out at a temperature of 55-60°C for 1-3 hours. Stirring the reaction mass was carried out using an electromagnetic stirrer.

After completion of the oligomerization reaction, the products were separated from the catalyst by washing with an alkaline solution and then with distilled water to a neutral environment. After oligomerization is completed, the resulting reaction mixture is separated into two layers. An ionic-liquid catalyst is deposited in the lower layer. And the top layer represents the oligomerization reaction product. After separating the catalyst from the reaction product by decantation, the ionic liquid was stored for further use in an inert environment. The oligomeric product, dried on punctured alumina, was fractionated. First, the unreacted monomer

was distilled off at atmospheric pressure. Distillation was then continued under vacuum. As a result, we got 3 factions:

- 1st fraction – unreacted monomer
- 2nd fraction (200-350C) – lower fractions containing mainly dimers, trimers, etc.
- 3rd fraction >350°C – synthetic fraction with a high index.

Result and discussion

Oligomerization of 1-octene in an ionic-liquid type catalytic system. In the composition of the ionic-liquid catalytic system, the proportion of AlCl₃ is in the range of 2-4 wt.% per olefin.

Table 1 shows the conditions and results of 1-octene oligomerization in the presence of ionic liquid catalytic systems

Table 1.

Oligomerization of 1-octene in ionic-liquid catalytic system (conditions: T = 60°C, catalyst amount 6% by monomer, atmosphere - nitrogen)

Monomer	The composition of the catalytic system	τ , hour	The concentration of Al, mol/l	Yield, mass %
C ₈	ILC1 1.3:1	3	0,18	72.2
	ILC2 1.7:1	3	0,214	75.5
	ILC3 1.2:1	1	0.12	53
	ILC4 1.1:1	1	0.11	60

The yields and molecular weight characteristics of ammonium hydrochloride and AlCl₃ are given in Table 2.

Table 2.

Yields and molecular weight characteristics of oligooctenes obtained in the presence of ILCs based on ammonium hydrochloride and AlCl₃

№	Monomer	The composition of the catalytic system	τ , hour	MWC			Yield, %
				M _w	M _n	M _w /M _n	
1	C ₈	ILC1 1.3:1	3	3000	2500	1.2	72.2
2		ILC2 1.7:1	3	3900	3700	1.05	75.5
3		ILC3 1.2:1	1	2500	2100	1.19	53
4		ILC4 1.1:1	1	2675	2300	1.16	60

With the increase of oligomerization temperature from 30°C to 60°C both the oligomerization rate and the yield of oligomerization products increase. In particular, at the identical concentrations of the catalyst (2 % mass. AlCl₃) and durations of reaction 3 hours the yield of oil fraction at 40°C constitute 63,0-78,2 %, and at 50°C - 71,0-83,2 %. At 60-65°C the process is practically accomplished in 2 hours with the yield of oligomerization products 96,1 %. However, the yield of oil fraction with boiling temperature above 320°C does not exceed 75 % mass.

However, they are more effective, than AlCl₃, used as a catalyst alone. Besides, the synthetic oligooctene oils, obtained on the ionic-liquid catalysts,

have more thermostability due to their oligoalkyl-naphthenic structure.

Using spectroscopic methods (IR, 13C NMR and PMR spectroscopy), the structures of the resulting oligooctenes oils obtained in the presence of chloroaluminate ionic-liquid catalysts were studied. The results of IR spectral analysis coincide with the data of PMR and 13C NMR spectroscopy. In the spectroscopic spectra of the obtained oil fractions obtained in the presence of an ion-liquid type catalytic system, there are signals corresponding to the chemical shifts of protons in naphthenic rings.

Quantities of the protons at the double bonds, calculated from the experimental PMR – spectra, are much

less than their theoretical quantity, calculated with the account of values of molecular masses of the received oligomers.

Identification of spectra for the products of the oligomerization process can lead to the conclusion that the oil fraction obtained from the oligomerization of 1-octene has practically no double bonds or a significant part of them has a structure of the $R_1R_2C=CR_3R_4$ type. The signals responsible for double bonds in the usual state are not detected in the PMR spectra. In addition to this, the identification of signals of naphthenic structures in the PMR spectra and ^{13}C NMR spectra. This indicates the oligoalkylnaphthenic nature of most of the molecules of the oligomerization process products. Identified signals in the ^{13}C NMR spectra, it can be said that the spectra contain signals of five-membered and six-membered naphthenic rings. Based on all these facts, one can judge that the cyclization reaction preferentially occurs in the last link of the growing oligomeric chain.

CONCLUSION

As a result of the researches carried out, it was shown the possibility to obtain oligoalkylnaphthenic

type synthetic oils and semisynthetic base oils on their basis, characterized by high viscosity index, high thermo-oxidative stability, low volatility and low freezing point, by oligomerization of octene-1 in the presence of sufficiently active chloroaluminate type ionic-liquid catalysts.

References

1. Seyidova X.H. α -Olefinlərin oliqomerləşməsi və polimerləşməsi sahəsində müasir vəziyyət. /Journal of Baku Engineering University and Biology. Chemistry and Biology, V.6, N.1, 2022, s. 19-31.
2. Azizov A.H., Aliyeva R.V. Asgerova Kh. H. Oligoalkylnaphthenic (C6-C12) oils obtained in the presence of Ti-containing ionic-liquid catalysts // Green and Suitable chemistry, 2013, №3, p. 18-26.
3. Seyidova X.H., Nəcəfova-Əliyeva G.S., Babaşova Y.M., Aliyeva R.V., Əliyeva F.X. Ion mayeləri iştirakında sintez olunmuş (oliqo)alkilləşmiş məhsullar əsasında kompozisiyalar/ Proceedings Of Azerbaijan High Technical Educational Institutions, 2024, V26, Is 2, p. 317-322.